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Library Management Strategies and Children's Reading Habit in Public Primary Schools in Port Harcourt Local Government Area of Rivers State

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ABSTRACT

Library management strategies play a crucial role in shaping children's reading habit, especially at the foundational level of education. This study examined library management strategies and children's reading habit in public primary schools in Port Harcourt City Local Government Area. Three specific objectives, three research questions, and three null hypotheses guided the study. The research design adopted for the study was the correlational design. The population comprised 1,764 pupils in five public primary schools in Port Harcourt City Local Government Area, while a sample size of 287 pupils was drawn using the judgmental sampling technique. The instrument for data collection was a structured questionnaire titled Library Management Strategies and Children's Reading Habit Questionnaire (LMSCRHQ). Mean and standard deviation were used to answer the research questions, while Pearson Product Moment Correlation was used to test the null hypotheses at 0.05 level of significance. The findings revealed that there is a significant relationship between the variables of library management strategies (provision of age-appropriate materials, conducive physical environment, and continuous staff training) and children's reading habit in public primary schools in Port Harcourt City Local Government Area. The study concluded that effective library management strategies significantly enhance children's reading habit by creating supportive, engaging, and resourceful reading environments. Based on the findings, it was recommended, among others, that librarians should deliberately select and organise books according to pupils' age as proper matching of materials will reduce frustration and encourage consistent reading habits among children.

Keywords: Library, Library Management, Library Management Strategies, Children's Reading Habit

INTRODUCTION

Reading is a deliberate process of encoding pictorial signals into meaningful meanings. According to Wahyuni (2021), it is a creative process where readers engage with the text to create meaning. It is a means of communication that allows people to receive information. Reading is a vital activity that should improve students' understanding in all areas of life, not only academics. According to Abella et al. (2024), reading is the act of understanding the representation of symbols that are written and printed by looking at them, identifying them, and occasionally verbalizing these visual indicators. According to the aforementioned, reading is a term used to describe an interaction in which meaning encoded in visual stimuli by an author creates meaning in the reader's mind. It entails the identification of printed or written

symbols that function as stimuli for the recall or meaning through the intellectual manipulation of concepts already held by the reader (Wiche and Oporum, 2022). Any society's life revolves around reading since it helps uncover hidden information and expand on what is already known. According to Agbevivi and Adogpa (2022), a society's level of engagement with written language may be used to gauge its level of cultural, scientific, and sociopolitical development.

Reading is a vital activity that should improve children's understanding in many areas of life, not just academics. It involves seeing, recognizing, and articulating textual signs in order to comprehend them. According to Aisyah and Wibowo (2025), reading is a notion used to describe an interaction in which meaning encoded in visual stimuli by a writer creates meaning in the reader's mind. According to Campilla and Cariño (2024), reading is not only incredibly powerful in helping students progress, but it is also vital to human existence in this era of information overload. Through reading, children acquire essential knowledge require for life success. The act of reading is best cultivated at young age as it encourages strong mental growth. An essential segment of childhood development is mental or cognitive development which reading encourages. Chusniawati et al. (2025), postulated that children who do not read well during elementary school are likely to have poor reading habit throughout their lifetime. Neglecting the act of reading gives birth to unnecessary disaster in the community. Hence, the need for the development of a good reading habit.

One of the essential building blocks for learning and creating a literate culture capable of competing with the rest of the world is the habit of reading. It involves helping kids develop a good attitude about reading over time (Agbevivi & Adogpa, 2022). Dominic (2025) asserted that while very few students strive to read for pleasure, they do have decent reading habits during test periods. The majority of students now use their reading time to watch movies and play games. Children's reading habits and lifetime literacy are greatly enhanced by efficient library administration (Mmejim & Oporum, 2022). Libraries, particularly school libraries, are dynamic learning spaces where kids participate in reading, storytelling, and other literacy-building activities in addition to being collections of books. The management of school libraries must be prioritized if reading is to become a regular activity for kids. This is because a library may assist kids develop healthy reading habits and achieve successful reading outcomes. This study, therefore, sought to examine library management strategies and children's reading habit in public primary schools in Port Harcourt Local Government Area of Rivers State.

Statement of the Problem

Librarians, educators, parents, and legislators, especially in Nigeria, have been increasingly concerned in recent years about fostering strong reading habits in children attending public primary schools. Basic reading is an essential ability that supports language learning, cognitive development, and lifelong learning in addition to being a necessary scholastic prerequisite. Nevertheless, many students in public primary schools exhibit poor reading habits, which are typified by a lack of interest in voluntary reading and inadequate comprehension abilities, despite the acknowledged significance of early reading engagement. This circumstance calls into doubt the efficacy of the current school support systems, particularly the library's function as a focal point for fostering a culture of reading.

The type and efficacy of library management techniques used in schools is one of the key elements that directly influences kids' reading habits. School libraries should ideally offer organized, engaging, and resource-rich spaces that inspire kids to explore books and cultivate a love of reading. However, libraries are either underused, poorly run, or ill-equipped in a lot of public elementary schools. Libraries' capacity to act as catalysts for reading development is severely hampered by problems such a lack of age-appropriate materials, inadequate resource organization, a lack of interesting reading programs, and a lack of professional help from qualified librarians. Children are less likely to interact meaningfully with library materials when management practices are ineffective or inconsistent, which limits their chances of forming long-term reading habits. Therefore, there is a pressing need to examine the relationship between library management strategies and children's reading habits, with a view to identifying practical approaches that can strengthen library services, enhance reading engagement, and ultimately improve educational outcomes among primary school pupils in the region.

Purpose of the Study

The purpose of this study is to examine the relationship that exist between library management strategies and children's reading habit in public primary schools in Port Harcourt City Local Government Area of Rivers State. Specifically, the researcher sought to:

- i Investigate the relationship between provision of age-appropriate materials and children's reading habit in public primary schools in Port Harcourt City Local Government Area of Rivers State.
- ii Ascertain the relationship between conducive physical environment and children's reading habit in public primary schools in Port Harcourt City Local Government Area of Rivers State.
- iii Establish the relationship between continuous staff training and children's reading habit in public primary schools in Port Harcourt City Local Government Area of Rivers State.

Research Questions

The research questions that guided this study were as follows:

- i What is the relationship between provision of age-appropriate materials and children's reading habit in public primary schools in Port Harcourt City Local Government Area of Rivers State.
- ii What is the relationship between conducive physical environment and children's reading habit in public primary schools in Port Harcourt City Local Government Area of Rivers State.
- iii What is the relationship between continuous staff training and children's reading habit in public primary schools in Port Harcourt City Local Government Area of Rivers State.

Hypotheses

The research was guided by the following null hypotheses:

Ho₁: There is no significant relationship between provision of age-appropriate materials and children's reading habit in public primary schools in Port Harcourt City Local Government Area of Rivers State.

Ho₂: There is no significant relationship between conducive physical environment and children's reading habit in public primary schools in Port Harcourt City Local Government Area of Rivers State.

Ho₃: There is no significant relationship between continuous staff training and children's reading habit in public primary schools in Port Harcourt City Local Government Area of Rivers State.

Review of Related Literature

Children's Reading Habit

Reading is a crucial activity that helps kids develop their language and communication abilities as well as their reading habits. Children who are regularly exposed to reading from a young age acquire familiarity, enthusiasm, and eventually a pattern around reading activities, according to Aisyah and Wibowo (2025). Reading becomes an enjoyable and self-motivated activity as a result of this regular interaction. According to Agbevivi and Adogpa (2022), reading is the foundation of information acquisition, and when kids learn to read at a young age, it becomes central to their overall educational development. In this regard, children's reading habit is built through repeated exposure, encouragement, and the creation of positive reading experiences that make them develop a lasting interest in books.

The assistance that librarians give is directly related to the growth of children's reading habits. According to Wahyuni (2021), reading exposes kids to a variety of life experiences that they would find difficult to learn through face-to-face engagement. This suggests that children are more likely to develop a regular reading habit when they are led and given enough reading materials, time, and interesting activities. Children's attention is maintained and their reading habit is gradually strengthened when librarians assist in providing an engaging reading environment (Cremin & Scholes, 2024). Fostering a strong reading habit early in life becomes a necessary strategy for improving literacy outcomes and lifelong learning. Reading activities play a significant role in reinforcing children's reading habit by developing the foundational skills required for independent reading. Wiche and Oporum (2022) avowed that reading does not only enhance cognitive and linguistic development but also serves as the foundation upon which a strong and sustained reading habit is built among children.

Library Management Strategies

In order to effectively satisfy users' informational, educational, and recreational requirements, library administration is a systematic process of organizing, coordinating, and administering library resources, services, and operations. Mmejim and Opurum (2022) state that in order to make sure the library is in line with its mission, vision, and user expectations, it involves making decisions regarding the selection, acquisition, organization, preservation, and dissemination of information products as well as supervising personnel management, financial and infrastructure planning, and technology integration. According to Lovely Professional University (2013), library management is the effective and efficient arrangement of materials (information resources), equipment, personnel, and funds in order to accomplish the library's objectives. Planning, organizing, staffing, budgeting, and evaluating services in a way that fosters students' social and cognitive development are all components of effective library administration.

Matching library services to the needs of the community they serve is another aspect of library management that goes beyond simple administrative processes. A well-run library evaluates the information, reading, and research needs of its patrons and adjusts its resources, services, and activities accordingly (Campilla and Cariño 2024). This implies that managing libraries requires continual service review, strategies for collection expansion, staff training, and the application of modern technology to enhance competency. This ensures that libraries will remain relevant in an information society that is changing quickly (Mmejim and Opurum, 2022). The methods, approaches, and procedures that librarians employ to establish and preserve a structured, effective, and encouraging reading environment are at the heart of library administration. It emphasizes creating routines, encouraging positive behavior, providing clear expectations, and skillfully handling interruptions. The administration of the library makes sure that it is prepared to facilitate various learning activities, pleasant, well-lit, ventilated, and well-organized.

Provision of Age-Appropriate Materials and Children's Reading Habit

Library resources that are carefully chosen to correspond with children's developmental phases, cognitive capacities, and reading levels are referred to as age-appropriate materials (Merga, 2023). These resources are made to accommodate children of various ages in terms of language proficiency, attention span, and comprehension ability. While older children are given more intricate plots, a wider vocabulary, and subject-specific materials, younger children are typically given picture books, straightforward stories, and visually captivating texts. Age-appropriate reading resources, according to Adkins et al. (2019), provide a balanced reading experience that fosters steady intellectual development and reading confidence. Age-appropriate materials take into account children's emotional and social development in addition to readability. The themes, characters, and messages embedded in such resources are structured to reflect children's real-life experiences, moral understanding, and curiosity about the world around them.

Materials that are culturally relevant, ethically sound, and engaging help children connect personally with what they read, thereby increasing motivation and interest. Soulen and Tedrow (2021) expressed that when children encounter texts that resonate with their experiences and developmental needs, they are more likely to develop positive attitudes toward reading and engage in it voluntarily. According to Gordon and Cicchetti (2023), long-term literacy development and maintained reading habits are greatly aided by the availability of age-appropriate resources. Children have more delight and fewer disappointments when they regularly access resources that are appropriate for their level, which encourages consistent reading behavior. According to Merga and Roni (2017), libraries that place a high priority on the accessibility, availability, and frequent updating of these resources foster an atmosphere that makes reading enjoyable and meaningful. Age-appropriate resources are therefore a fundamental component in developing a positive reading habit that supports academic performance as well as lifetime learning and personal growth.

Conducive Physical Environment and Children's Reading Habit

In the context of a school library, the physical environment refers to the state of the immediate surroundings in which activities are conducted. According to Adetayo et al. (2015), it is essential in forming kids' reading habits. The physical setting of a library has a big impact on how kids engage with reading materials, just as a workplace has an impact on workers' productivity. Cleanliness, lighting,

ventilation, seating arrangements, noise levels, and overall visual appeal are all aspects of the library environment. Together, these factors decide whether the area is encouraging or deterring to young readers. According to Beard and Dale (2010), as no institution functions in a vacuum, the quality of a library's surroundings has a significant impact on how well it fosters a reading habit. While a badly maintained setting may lower interest and limit engagement, a well-organized and appealing library area naturally piques children's curiosity and encourages them to spend more time reading.

The physical environment of the library can be viewed through interconnected dimensions that influence children's reading behaviour. Seal (2015) identified technical, human, and organisational environments as key components of any library setting. When it comes to children's reading, the technological environment includes things like furniture, lighting, ventilation, and bookshelf layout, all of which need to be adjusted to meet the demands of the kids. For example, comfortable and focused reading is improved by kid-friendly sitting, sufficient illumination, and appropriate space (Beard & Dale, 2010). On the other hand, youngsters may become distracted and find it difficult to read for extended periods of time in a noisy, crowded, or poorly ventilated library. Sullivan (2010) emphasized that a cozy and enjoyable setting improves performance, which in this instance translates into increased children's reading engagement. Children are more likely to have favorable attitudes about reading and actively engage in reading activities when they are given a peaceful, well-organized, and aesthetically pleasing environment.

Continuous Staff Training and Children's Reading Habit

The term "staff training" is a methodical, ongoing process that gives workers the information, abilities, competences, and attitudes needed to carry out their jobs successfully. According to Akintola et al. (2025), it entails planned activities including seminars, workshops, coaching, mentoring, and on-the-job training intended to enhance job performance and match workers with organizational objectives. To ensure that librarians continue to be successful in encouraging children to read, ongoing staff training is crucial. In order to stay up to date with new literacy practices, technology, and child-centered learning techniques, staff members in the ever-evolving fields of education and library services must constantly refresh their knowledge and abilities. Continuous staff training can therefore be seen as a systematic process through which librarians acquire relevant competencies needed to support children's reading development. As Cangelosi and Dill (2025) noted in the context of professional growth, continuous staff training is central to strategic success in any organisation. When librarians participate in regular training such as workshops, seminars, and reading promotion programmes, they become more productive and better equipped to guide children in developing sustained reading habits.

According to Gezdur and Bhattacharjya, ongoing staff training improves librarians' ability to carry out their duties in ways that directly promote kids' reading engagement. (2025) emphasized that the goal of staff training is to enhance workers' capacity to do their jobs effectively. This suggests that qualified librarians are better at choosing suitable reading materials, planning interesting reading programs, and using interactive techniques that inspire kids to read. According to Cangelosi and Dill (2025), employees who possess certain abilities outperform those who do not. Continuous training programmes such as coaching, mentoring, and exposure to innovative literacy tools therefore enable librarians to inspire, challenge, and stimulate children to develop interest and consistency in reading. Ongoing staff training is an essential method for enhancing each librarian's proficiency as well as the general efficacy of library services in encouraging kids to read. Professional development is crucial for creating qualified librarians who can satisfy present and future library demands, according to Akintola et al. (2025). Through ongoing training, librarians acquire the information, abilities, and attitudes needed to manage resources effectively, establish programs that promote children's voluntary reading, and create surroundings that are favorable to reading.

METHODOLOGY

The study employed a correlational research design. 1764 pupils found in 5 public primary schools in Port Harcourt Local Government Area of Rivers State constitute the population of the study (River State Universal Basic Education Board, 2025). The sample of the study was 287 pupils from 5 public primary

schools in Port Harcourt Local Government Area of Rivers State. The researcher adopted the judgmental sampling technique as consideration was limited to Basic Five pupils because they generally demonstrate a higher level of reasoning ability. Also, most schools have fewer pupils in Basic Six, as most pupils take their final examinations in Basic Five. The judgmental sampling technique was most suitable as it enable the researcher to select elements that constitute the sample from the population, based on certain attributes.

The instrument used for the collection of data was a structured questionnaire titled: Library Management Strategies and Children’s Reading Habit Questionnaire (LMSCRHQ). The questionnaire was structured using a four point likert scale of Strongly Agree (SA)⁴, Agree (A)³, Disagree (D)², and Strongly Disagree (SD)¹. In interpreting the responses from the four-point Likert scale, the study adopted a decision threshold of 2.50 as the criterion mean. The Split-half method was the method employed to assess the instrument’s reliability. Mean and standard deviation were used to answer the research questions while the Pearson Product Moment Correlation Coefficient was used to test the null hypotheses at 0.05 level of significance.

ANALYSIS OF DATA AND RESULTS

Table 1: Questionnaire Response Rate

Respondents	Number Administered	Number Retrieved	Number Used	Percentage Used
Pupils	287	281	277	97%

Source: Field Data, 2026

Table 1 above shows the breakdown of questionnaires administered, retrieved and used for analysis of the study. The table indicates that 287 questionnaires were administered, 281 retrieved from the pupils while 277 (97%) were used for analysis of the study. 4 out of the 281 retrieved questionnaires were wrongly filled.

Research Questions

Research Question 1: *What is the relationship between provision of age-appropriate materials and children’s reading habit in public primary schools in Port Harcourt City Local Government Area of Rivers State.*

Table 2: Summary of descriptive statistics on the relationship between provision of age-appropriate materials and children’s reading habit in public primary schools

S/N	ITEMS	\bar{x}	SD	REMARK
1	The books in my school library are easy for me to understand	2.71	.809	Agree
2	I enjoy reading the storybooks available in the library	2.89	.737	Agree
3	The pictures and stories in the books make me want to read more	2.90	.995	Agree
4	I find books in the library that match my class level	3.01	.791	Agree
5	The books in my school library capture some of the topics treated in class	2.84	.913	Agree
	Grand Mean (\bar{x})	2.87		Agree

Source: Field Data, 2026

This shows the item-by-item analysis on the relationship between provision of age-appropriate materials and children’s reading habit in public primary schools in Port Harcourt City Local Government Area of Rivers State. The results indicate that all the items recorded mean scores above the criterion mean of 2.50, showing a general trend of agreement among respondents. Specifically, the item on finding books that match pupils’ class level ($\bar{x} = 3.01$) recorded the highest mean score, followed by the item on pictures and stories motivating reading ($\bar{x} = 2.90$), and enjoyment of storybooks ($\bar{x} = 2.89$). Similarly, the relevance of books to classroom topics ($\bar{x} = 2.84$) and ease of understanding the books ($\bar{x} = 2.71$) also fall within the agreement range, The cluster of mean scores above 2.50 indicates that respondents perceive the materials in the library as appropriate to their age and level,

Research Question 2: *What is the relationship between conducive physical environment and children's reading habit in public primary schools in Port Harcourt City Local Government Area of Rivers State.*

Table 3 Summary of descriptive statistics on the relationship between conducive physical environment and children's reading habit in public primary schools

S/N	ITEMS	\bar{X}	SD	REMARK
6	The library is a quiet place where I can read without disturbance	2.75	.962	Agree
7	The chairs and tables in the library make me comfortable when reading	2.90	.817	Agree
8	The library is clean and makes me want to stay and read	2.61	.747	Agree
9	The library is spacious enough to allow for natural lighting, which helps me to read	2.91	.901	Agree
10	I enjoy going to the library because it is a nice place to read	2.75	.802	Agree
	Grand Mean (\bar{x})	2.78		Agree

Source: *Field Data, 2026*

This shows the item-by-item analysis on the relationship between conducive physical environment and children's reading habit in public primary schools in Port Harcourt City Local Government Area of Rivers State. The findings reveal that all the items recorded mean scores above the criterion mean of 2.50, indicating a general agreement among respondents. The item on the library being spacious with adequate natural lighting ($\bar{x} = 2.91$) recorded the highest mean score, closely followed by comfort of chairs and tables ($\bar{x} = 2.90$). The quietness of the library ($\bar{x} = 2.75$) and enjoyment of visiting the library ($\bar{x} = 2.75$) also fall within the agreement range, while cleanliness of the library ($\bar{x} = 2.61$) recorded the lowest mean score, though still above the benchmark. The cluster of mean scores above 2.50 indicates that respondents perceive the library environment as conducive.

Research Question 3: *What is the relationship between continuous staff training and children's reading habit in public primary schools in Port Harcourt City Local Government Area of Rivers State.*

Table 4: Summary of descriptive statistics on the relationship between continuous staff training and children's reading habit in public primary schools

S/N	ITEMS	\bar{X}	SD	REMARK
11	The librarian helps me choose books that I like	2.71	.782	Agree
12	The librarian teaches me how to read better	2.62	.817	Agree
13	The librarian tells us interesting stories that make me want to read	2.81	.937	Agree
14	The librarian encourages me to read more books	2.82	.937	Agree
15	I feel happy reading in the library because of the librarian's help	2.60	.729	Agree
	Grand Mean (\bar{x})	2.71		Agree

Source: *Field Data, 2026*

This shows the item-by-item analysis on the relationship between continuous staff training and children's reading habit. The results indicate that all items recorded mean scores above the benchmark of 2.50, reflecting general agreement. Encouragement from the librarian ($\bar{x} = 2.82$) and storytelling activities ($\bar{x} = 2.81$) ranked highest, followed by assistance in book selection ($\bar{x} = 2.71$). Teaching reading skills ($\bar{x} = 2.62$) and creating a happy reading experience ($\bar{x} = 2.60$) were also positively rated. This implies that continuous staff training, as reflected in librarians' supportive roles improves children's reading habit.

Hypotheses Testing

Ho₁: There is no significant relationship between provision of age-appropriate materials and children’s reading habit in public primary schools in Port Harcourt City Local Government Area of Rivers State.

Table 5: Summary of Pearson Product Moment Correlation on the relationship between provision of age-appropriate materials and children’s reading habit

Variables		Provision of Age-appropriate Materials	Children’s Reading Habit
Provision of Age-appropriate Materials	Pearson Correlation	1	.910**
	Sig. (2-tailed)		.000
	N	277	277
	Pearson Correlation	.910**	1
Children’s Reading Habit	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000	
	N	277	277

Source: Field Data, 2026

The result of hypothesis one in Table 5 shows a correlation coefficient (r) of .910, indicating a very strong positive relationship between provision of age-appropriate materials and children’s reading habit. The p-value of .000 is less than 0.05, showing that the relationship is statistically significant. Therefore, the null hypothesis one is rejected, and the alternative hypothesis is accepted. This means there is a significant relationship between provision of age-appropriate materials and children’s reading habit in public primary schools in Port Harcourt City Local Government Area of Rivers State.

Ho₂: There is no significant relationship between conducive physical environment and children’s reading habit in public primary schools in Port Harcourt City Local Government Area of Rivers State.

Table 6: Summary of Pearson Product Moment Correlation on the relationship between conducive physical environment and children’s reading habit

Variables		Conducive Physical Environment	Children’s Reading Habit
Conducive Physical Environment	Pearson Correlation	1	.717**
	Sig. (2-tailed)		.000
	N	277	277
	Pearson Correlation	.717**	1
Children’s Reading Habit	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000	
	N	277	277

Source: Field Data, 2026

The result of hypothesis two in Table 6 shows a correlation coefficient (r) of .717, indicating a high positive relationship between conducive physical environment and children’s reading habit. The p-value of .000 is less than 0.05, showing that the relationship is statistically significant. Therefore, the null hypothesis two is rejected, and the alternative hypothesis is accepted. This means there is a significant relationship between conducive physical environment and children’s reading habit in public primary schools in Port Harcourt City Local Government Area of Rivers State.

Ho₃: There is no significant relationship between continuous staff training and children’s reading habit in public primary schools in Port Harcourt City Local Government Area of Rivers State.

Table 7: Summary of Pearson Product Moment Correlation on the relationship between continuous staff training and children’s reading habit

Variables		Conducive Physical Environment	Children’s Reading Habit
Conducive Physical Environment	Pearson Correlation	1	.783**
	Sig. (2-tailed)		.000
	N	277	277
	Pearson Correlation	.783**	1
Children’s Reading Habit	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000	
	N	277	277

Source: Field Data, 2026

The result of hypothesis three in Table 7 shows a correlation coefficient (r) of .783, indicating a high positive relationship between continuous staff training and children’s reading habit. The p-value of .000 is less than 0.05, showing that the relationship is statistically significant. Therefore, the null hypothesis three is rejected, and the alternative hypothesis is accepted. This means there is a significant relationship between continuous staff training and children’s reading habit in public primary schools in Port Harcourt City Local Government Area of Rivers State.

DISCUSSION OF FINDINGS

Provision of Age-Appropriate Materials and Children’s Reading Habit

The result of hypothesis one shows that there is significant and positive relationship between the provision of age-appropriate materials and children’s reading habit in public primary schools in Port Harcourt City Local Government Area of Rivers State. This infers that the provision of age-appropriate materials play essential roles in promoting children’s reading habit. The significant relationship between provision of age-appropriate materials and children’s reading habit highlights the importance of aligning library resources with children’s developmental stages, cognitive abilities, and reading levels. This finding is consistent with Merga (2023), who avowed that materials that match children’s language competence, attention span, and comprehension capacity, ranging from picture books and novels are essential for developing a good reading habit. When children interact with texts that are meaningful and suited to their level, they experience less frustration and more enjoyment, which strengthens their reading habit and builds confidence in reading (Adkins et al., 2019). Gordon and Cicchetti (2023) expressed that when materials are suitably matched to children’s levels, they become easier to understand, more engaging, and less frustrating. This balance encourages children to read willingly and repeatedly, which is essential for building a consistent reading habit.

Conducive Physical Environment and Children’s Reading Habit

The result of hypothesis two shows that there is a significant and positive relationship between conducive physical environment and children’s reading habit in public primary schools in Port Harcourt City Local Government Area of Rivers State. This implies that the physical environment plays a vital role in promoting children’s reading habit. This finding aligns with Adetayo et al. (2015) who avowed that the effectiveness of any library is largely dependent on the quality of its environment. Conversely, a noisy, overcrowded, or poorly ventilated library may discourage children from engaging in reading activities (Seal, 2015). Supporting this view, Beard and Dale (2010) emphasised that a comfortable and pleasant environment enhances performance, which in this context translates to improved reading engagement. Therefore, a well-organised, calm, and attractive library environment fosters positive reading attitudes and strengthens children’s reading habit.

Continuous Staff Training and Children's Reading Habit

The result of hypothesis three shows that there is a significant and positive relationship between continuous staff training and children's reading habit in public primary schools in Port Harcourt City Local Government Area of Rivers State. This suggests that continuous staff training plays a crucial role in promoting children's reading habit. This aligns with Cangelosi and Dill (2025), who noted that continuous professional development is essential for achieving effectiveness in any library. The findings further indicate that trained librarians are better positioned to improve children's reading behaviour through their daily interactions. For instance, children reported that librarians encourage them to read more books and create a happy reading experience in the library. These responses reflect the practical impact of continuous staff training, as librarians who undergo regular training are more capable of guiding, motivating, and engaging children in reading activities Akintola et al. (2025) supports this by stating that staff training improves librarians' ability to perform their duties productively, while Gezdu and Bhattacharjya. (2025), avowed that skilled and knowledgeable staff perform better in stimulating learners' interest. Akintola et al. (2025) opines that continuous staff training strengthens the overall effectiveness of library services in fostering children's reading habit. Through training programmes such as workshops, seminars, mentoring, and exposure to modern literacy tools, librarians develop the competence to create engaging reading environments and implement programmes that encourage voluntary reading.

CONCLUSION

This study examined library management strategies and children's reading habit in public primary schools in Port Harcourt City Local Government Area of Rivers State, based on the understanding that the library serves as a vital platform for developing children's literacy, cognitive growth, and lifelong learning. It is clear that the way a library is managed significantly affects children's willingness to engage in reading, interact with books, and develop sustained reading habits. Specifically, the study revealed that the provision of age-appropriate materials, conducive physical environment and continuous staff training relate with children's reading habit. Library management enhances children's interest and creates a comfortable and attractive space that encourages regular reading engagement.

RECOMMENDATIONS

Based on the findings of the study, the following recommendations were made:

1. Librarians should deliberately select and organise books according to pupils' age as proper matching of materials will reduce frustration and encourage consistent reading habits among children.
2. Educational authorities like the Universal Basic Education, should invest in child-friendly furniture and adequate library space, as comfortable seating and proper arrangement of facilities will enhance children's reading experience and sustain their interest in library use.
3. School authorities should organise regular training programmes such as workshops, seminars, and mentoring sessions for school librarians, as this will equip them with modern skills to effectively guide and motivate children in reading.

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